

The Impact of Communicative Approach on Developing Students` Speaking Skills

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Abstract. *In the modern world, significant advancements have been observed in the field of Education, particularly in the teaching of foreign languages. The communicative language teaching approach has become an essential component of English teaching methods and continues to be extensively utilized by foreign language instructors. Additionally, linguists are actively focusing on and studying the topic of communicative language teaching.*

Key words: *communication, role playing, discussion, warming up, communicative language teaching, communicative method, a communicative perspective on language, communicative perspective on learning, "strong version", "weak version".*

The students' participation in speaking class is indicated by the involvement of the students in the class activity. In this case, the frequency and the duration of the students' speaking are the indicators of their participation. Therefore, the more frequent and the longer they are speaking, the better their participation in speaking class. Since the mid of the nineteenth century up to now, there have been many methods that are still recognized, such as Grammar, Translation method, Direct Method, Audio Lingual Method, Cognitive Approach, Communicative Approach.

In the following problem, the communicative approach will be presented briefly. The communicative approach as a way of teaching English as foreign language (EFL) students learn through using the language and have many opportunities to interact with each other and with the teacher.

While Nunan [8, 279] in Brown [3, 78] offers features to characteristic CLT:

1. An emphasis on learning to communicate through interaction in the target language.
2. The introduction of authentic text into the learning situation.
3. The provision of opportunities for learner to focus, not only on languages but also on the learning process itself.
4. An enhancement of the learners own personal experiences as important contributing elements to classroom learning.
5. An attempt to link classroom language learning with language activation outside the classroom.

Communicative approach can be divided into two versions as stated by some linguists:

"There is a 'strong' version of the communicative approach and a 'weak' version which has become more or less standard practice in the last ten years, stresses the importance of providing learners with opportunities to use their English for communicative purposes and, characteristically, attempts to integrate such activities into a wider program of language teaching. The 'strong' version of communicative teaching on the other hand, advances the claim that language is acquired through communication, so that it is not merely a question of activating an existing but inert knowledge system

itself. If the former could be described as 'learning to use' English, the latter entails 'using English to learn it'.

Furthermore, a methodological approach to the teaching of languages which takes of input, (both roughly-and finely-tuned), practice, and communication input. Many writers have called it the communicative approach to language teaching. Thus is because its aims are overtly communicative and great emphasis, as we have see, is paced on training students to use language for communication. The communicative approach is, then, an umbrella term to describe methodology which teaches students how to communicative efficiently and which lays emphasis on the teaching of communicative value and, in some cases, the teaching of language functions. Perhaps, for the present, we shall have to be satisfied that this is as close as we can get to a definition of CLT. In addition, William puts forward the major characteristics of CLT appear to be three. At the level of syllabus design the dominant feature is relevance to learners' need; at the level of methodology the concern is with meaningful communication; at the level of material it with authenticity.

Brown [4, 213] offers the following four interconnected characteristics as a definition of CLT: (1) Classroom goals are focused on all of the components of communicative competence and not restricted to the grammatical or linguistic competence. (2) Form is not the primary framework for organizing and sequencing lessons. Function is the framework through which forms is taught. (3) Accuracy is secondary to conveying a message. Fluency may take on more importance than accuracy. The ultimate criterion for communicative success is the actual transmission and receiving odd intended meaning. (4) In the communicative classroom, students ultimately have to use the, language, productively and receptively, in unrehearsed context. 'Communicative language teaching' is one, which recognize the teaching of 'communicative competence' as its aim. It is on this level of aim that such a language teaching distinguishes itself from more traditional approaches where the emphasis is heavily on teaching structural competence. We may thus see the revision of aims as enrichment an acceptance that there are further dimension of language, which need teaching.

Mastering English for the students is very important since the skill can be the key to study other knowledge. But sometimes the teacher finds difficulties in transferring the skill since there are many aspects involved. One of the difficulties is related to mastering speaking skills, since English is not a daily life language, even it is in formal schools.

Preliminary study conducted by the researcher related to speaking ability was as follows. First, the students are often inhibited about trying to say something in foreign language in the classroom, sometimes they worried about making mistakes or simply shy of the attention that their speech is attracted. It will make them loose of their confidence. Second, students are usually having nothing to say because they cannot think of anything to say. Third, students are easier to speak using their mother tongue rather than English. It is because English is not generally used in their daily life.

The communicative approach in language teaching starts from a theory of language as communication. The goal of language teaching is to develop what was referred to as 'communicative competence'. It was definition of what a speaker needs to know in order to be communicatively competent in a speech community. Communicative Language Teaching is one of the methods which suites with the goal of language teaching especially in teaching speaking. According to Hammer [6, 84], Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is the name which was given to a set of beliefs which included not only about what aspects of language to teach, but also a shift in emphasis in how to teach.

The activities in CLT typically involve students in real or realistic communication, where the accuracy of language they use is less important than successful achievement of the communicative task they are performing. Students should have a desire to communicate something. They should focuses on the content of what they are saying rather than on a particular language form. It means that CLT has an aim at improving students' ability to communicate in oral. That statement is supported by Wu [11, 50-53], he stated that CLT emphasizes the speaking skill in order to improve their communicative ability by focusing on meaning, and refuses error correction for maintaining the conversation.

There are some techniques that can be used by the teacher in teaching speaking by using CLT. According to Applebaum [1, 266-270], there are some examples of communicative activities that can be used by the teacher to teach speaking such as role play, language games, and scramble sentences. On the other hand, Banciu [2, 97] stated that there are some classroom activities that frequently used in CLT such as role play, interviews, information gap, games, language exchanges, surveys and pair work. That statements were supported by Richard [9, 169] who stated that a variety of games and role plays have been prepared to support CLT classes.

Role plays are very important in CLT because they give students an opportunity to practice communicating in different social contexts and in different social roles. On the other hand, Harmer [7, 92] stated that role play activities are those where the students are asked to imagine that they are in different students and act accordingly. He gives the example of role play that is the students act a real-life encounter (such as a business meeting, an encounter in an airplane cabin, or an interview) as if they were doing in the real life. Applebaum [1, 269] also stated an example of role play is one student will play as the waiter or waitress and the others will be the customer in the restaurant. In other hand, Brown [4, 174] stated other example of role play is the student will pretend as a tourist asking for direction or pretend as a customer who wants to buy a necklace with lower price in a market.

It may be concluded that role play let the students to act in different context and role where the role they play is taken from their real life. It makes them easier to do the role play because it happened in their daily life. They need to act, to interpret, express and negotiate meaning in a new language. Anyway it can be said that role play let the students to act in different context and role where the role they play is taken from their real life. It makes them easier to do the role play because it happened in their daily life. They need to act, to interpret, express and negotiate meaning in a new language.

According to the scientific research made by some linguists, there are eight steps in role playing. The steps and explanations are as follow: 1) 'Warming Up' the Group (Problem Confrontation): This first step of role play presents a problem for the group where they need to learn ways dealing with the problem. This step are consists of two parts. The first part is the teacher and the students decide a problem that should be discussed in role playing. In the second part, the teacher will explain the problem clearly, so the students will understand it well. 2) Selecting Participants for Role Playing: In selecting participants, the teacher asks the students to describe the character in the topic (problem) that has been selected. Students who can explain the character in certain will be chosen to play the character. 3) Setting the Stage: In this step, the role player prepares plan in briefly about what they are going to do. They do not permitted to bring any dialogue, so the action will take naturally by exploring their idea in the action. 4) Preparing the Audience to be Participating Observer: In this section, listening skill is needed to make the observing group easier understand the idea of role player. By understanding the role player, they may give other alternatives to help the role player solve the problem. 5) Role Playing (the Enactment): In this section, the role player should live the situation, respond to another's speech and action as they feel the people in those roles would behave. Players must think and feel by themselves, spontaneously reacting to the developing situation. 6) Discussion and Evaluation: This part is one of the most vital steps of role playing. The researcher indicated that the actual taking of roles may have the greatest influence on attitudinal changes; it is in the give-and-take of discussion that problem-solving procedures are refined and learned. The observers are in position to see more consequences to proposals more easily and to see more alternatives problem solving. 7) The Reenactment (Further Role Playing and Discussion): The role player may play their roles over and over again, changing their interpretations and solution. It also may for the new actor to take over the role to demonstrate other interpretations and solutions. 8) Sharing Experience and Generalizing: After a number of alternatives and their consequences have been enacted and discussed, the teacher may ask "has something like this ever happened to someone you know?" These sharing experiences, this exploration of consequences of behavior, achieve several important objectives such as it helps anxious young people to discover that their problem are shared by other people, provides opportunity for the teacher through his supportive leadership, to gain the confidence of the group. The aspect that is intended to improve in this research is speaking ability. Brown [5, 140] stated that speaking is a productive skill that can be directly and empirically observed by the accuracy and

effectiveness of test-takers listening skill, which necessarily compromises the reliability and validity of oral production test. On other hand, Thornbury [10, 1] stated that “speaking is the ability to speak fluently followed naturally from the teaching of grammar and vocabulary, with bit pronunciation thrown in, and involves both a command of certain skills and several types of knowledge”. From the statements, it may be concluded that speaking is the ability to speak fluently by using the target language in order to interact or communicate with others.

The aspects of speaking to be improver are: 1) Fluency meaning the capability of someone to speak in normal speed with few pauses then to continue to speak. Not only about pausing, but also about how to express their idea. It is necessary for the students not to make so many pauses and repetition when they speak. 2) Vocabulary meaning knowledge about vocabulary is needed by the students to understand a sentence. 3) Pronunciation meaning the articulation of word such as volume, stress, pausing, etc. The students should know well how to pronounce a word. It uses to make the conversation easier to understand and 4) Grammar. Grammar in spoken is different from grammar in writing. Students may say a sentence not in correct form in spoken, but the knowledge of grammar is still needed by the students to make sentences. Related to the use of CLT to improve students’ speaking skill, there is no doubt that it logically does. CLT emphasizes the speaking skill in order to improve their communicative ability by focusing on meaning, and refuse error correction for maintaining the conversation and it focuses on real oral communication where the student is the centered.

To conclude, in classes’ activity, the teacher let the students act as negotiator for each other and express their idea by letting them say what they want to say. The teacher himself acts as a facilitator and advisor to help the students by giving feedback to each student.

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